

CHRISTIAN MONASTERIES OF DZAMA GORGE

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Georgian Christian monastic settlements, both in Georgia and abroad, have played a major role in shaping Christian culture and consciousness for centuries. The abolition of Georgian statehood by the Russian Empire and the subsequent era of Bolshevism caused remarkable damage to the values on which Georgian statehood stood. Especially, Christian temples were being destroyed and taken on the verge of destruction during the communist governance. This applies not only to Christian temples but also to other religious institutions. Representatives of different denominations and ethnicities lived permanently in Georgia, and accordingly, there were many mosques, synagogues, and Catholic and Lutheran temples. Many sites of cultural heritage have been sacrificed by Bolshevik ideology.

Ethnic conflicts inspired in Georgia in the post-Soviet period, along with the violation of territorial integrity, also led to the loss of ancient Christian monastic settlements. With the blessing of His Holiness and Beatitude Ilia II, especially the restoration and construction of monastic settlements were strengthened on the borders and ridges of the country.

Dzama gorge located on the Trialeti ridge has long been distinguished by the density of its population. A small number of eco-migrants and Ossetians lived here along with Georgians, who left the gorge in the 90s of the XX century. At present, the valley is especially distinguished by Christian temples, old or newly restored and built churches-monasteries.

Many temples built in the Dzama gorge, repeat the names of the temples in Tao-Klarjeti⁵⁹. Important is the Sarkineti Monastery, which is carved into the rock and today a liturgy is being held here. The temples caved in rocks in Georgia are Davit Gareji, Vardzia, and Mghvimevi Monastery in Kvirila gorge, near Chiatura. Also noteworthy is the cross-domed church of St. Vakhtang King, which is distinguished by its architectural style and painting. It is noteworthy that during the period of independence, several temples were established in Georgia which were named after the Holy King in Tbilisi, Batumi, Rustavi, Vani (Dzulekho Temple), and Sioni.

⁵⁹ Tao-Klarjeti was a historical-geographical part of Georgia, now it is on the territory of Turkey.

Monastic life in the Christian monasteries of the Dzama Gorge has been restored and is operational in 58 churches-monasteries.

The Orthodox Autocephalous Church of Georgian has played a major role in the country's social, political, economic, and cultural life. It was constantly on the lookout for the country and the nation. At the beginning of the XIX century, the arbitrary cancellation of the autocephaly by the Russian government led to the seizure of the property of the Georgian Church, and the dissolution of the dioceses. But Georgian society, along with the clergy, began to fight for the restoration of autocephaly. Despite a great struggle, the Autocephalous Church of Georgia was restored, but the struggle did not end. The Catholicos-Patriarch of Georgia Kirion II published the article "Expectations" in the magazine "Svetitskhoveli" (magazine "Svetitskhoveli", Expectations, Tb. 1917 N1) (only four issues of the magazine were published. Publication was suspended due to political situation), where he noted that the holder of centralist thought (Russia) would not reconcile with what the Church of Georgia intended for its sacred purpose; it would not tolerate territorial autocephaly, which is accompanied by the proper elevation of the Patriarch-Catholicos of Georgia and his supreme governance within the borders of the territory." Indeed, the fear of the Catholicos-Patriarch came to be true, and again the statehood of Georgia was abolished by Russia. The era of Bolshevism has done amazing damage to the values on which Georgian statehood has stood for centuries. In 1977, when Ilia II became the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia, there were 15 dioceses in the Georgian Orthodox Apostolic Church, the number of which has grown considerably and now includes 49 dioceses (including dioceses abroad).

Historically, monastic life was of great importance in the Georgian Orthodox Apostolic Church. Monasteries functioned not only as religious but also as cultural and educational centers. It was for this purpose that with the

blessing of His Holiness and Beatitude Ilia II, the monasteries of mothers and fathers were restored and established, which represent an important sanctuary of the Christian Church.

One of the dioceses of the Autocephalous Church of Georgia is the Ruis-Urbnisi Diocese of Shida Kartli (5th century). It unites the flock territories of two ancient theological cathedrals, Ruisi and Urbnisi, the separate mention of which dates back to the period after Vakhtang Gorgasali⁶⁰. The temples on the territory of the diocese are important monuments of Georgian spirituality and culture.

Shida Kartli historically included a territory that was bordered by: to the east - Aragvi, to the north - the Caucasus, to the west - the Likha ridge, to the south - the Trialeti ridge. The part of Shida Kartli which was located to the south of Mtkvari was called Gaghmamkhari. The name is found in documents of the late feudal era. There are differences of opinion regarding the term (Gvasalia J., Todria T., Political Boundaries of the Kingdom of Kakheti of the Late Feudal Period, "Historical Geographical Collection of Georgia", 1971, vol. 4; p. 45). Some scholars believe that Gaghmamkhari was called the right bank of the Mtkvari from Tashiskari to Mtskheta, and some part believes, that it is the nobility of the late feudal era - Satsitsiano. Today, the population of Kartli calls Gaghmamkhari the territory of historical Satsitsiano.

Satsitsiano was one of the important nobilities of the Kingdom of Kartli, which was formed in the XVI century and was divided into upper (Zemo) and lower (Kvemo) parts. Zemo Satsitsiano included Dzama gorge "up from Khvedureti to Damchkheralo" (The Georgian Chronicles ." Kartlis Tskhovreba, volume IV, p. 344), and Kvemo Satsitsiano included Nichbisi and its surrounding areas. (N. Berdzenishvili, Materials from the feudal relations of the XV century and from the History of the Caucasus, 1st collection, Tbilisi, 1937, p. 51). The Tsitsishvilis were commanders. Vakhushti Batonishvili mentions Satsitsiano in the fourth Saspaspeto (administrative unit in Georgia established during the King Parnavaz). It should be noted that where the first residence of the Panaskerteli-Tsitsishvilis was located is still unknown. However, their main fortresses were Dzama and Samtsevisi, where the Panaskertelis were to settle for the first time. (G. Chubinashvili, Materials for the Study of the Samtsevisi Temple. Georgian Art. Tb. 1998. pp. 23-25) The Samtsevisi Fortress-Hall played a great role in the protection of the nobility.

⁶⁰ Vakhtang Gorgasali was a king of Iberia, natively known as Kartli (eastern Georgia) in the second half of the 5th century. Fought against Iranians, united the country and gained ecclesiastical independence through the Byzantine Empire.

Dzama gorge did not represent the main highway of the country, however (there was even a custom in Mzovreti) (P. Zakaria, History of Georgian fortresses. Tb. 2002 pp. 357-363) this road to the Mtkvari gorge connected the main highway with the settlement located beyond the Trialeti ridge. Therefore, its protection was a concern of both the owner and the government. That is why large-scale fortresses such as Samtsevisi and Dzama fortresses were built. Dzama Gorge has been repeatedly invaded by the enemy, from Murvan Kru to the Ottoman-Kizilbashes, including “Lekianoba” (invasions of Lak people). Constant war, destruction, and looting emptied and ravaged the gorge by the end of the 18th century. Monastic life ceased to exist.

During the period of Russian colonialism, the Tsitsishvilis managed to restore the territory of the nobility, albeit temporarily⁶¹. The population was brought from Imereti and Java. Ossetians brought from Java settled in the villages of the Dzama gorge and lived with Georgians before the start of the ethnic conflict, which led to the formation of many mixed families in the gorge. The churches-monasteries and houses of the Tsitsishvilis in the gorge, especially from the Bolshevik era, begin to uproot from the ground.

From the 70s of the XX century, the restoration and construction of historical settlements on the borders and ridges of the country gradually began. Today, up to 50 temples have been restored and built in the Dzama Gorge. Before touching on the new temples, we should mention a few monasteries, which were traced and restored with the blessing and great efforts of Reverend Iobi, and also a great contribution was made by the Bishop Ephrem of Bolnisi. The finding of the former temples was carried out by these fathers. They first found the ruins of the Abukhali Monastery⁶², then with the help of the locals, they also discovered the Kozipha Temple. Vakhushiti Batonishvili notes that: "To the west is the gorge of Abukhali, here are many caves carved out of high rock ... to the west of this road is a rock as brilliant as gold, and at down to it is the monastery Kozipha, without doom, well-built, inside the mountain and hence revoked (the Georgian Chronicles. Vol. IV p. 345. Tbilisi 1973). After the search for the temples, the cleansing work was carried out by the fathers, and today there are already seven temples in Kozipha. Kozipha, the same Gugomi Church is a temple built at different times. Construction began in the VI-VII centuries and in the

⁶¹ In XIX century, as a result of re-administrative division by Russia, Tsitsitsianovs entered Gori's territory and the nobility was abolished.

⁶² Abukhalo is a former village. According to the 2002 census, the village is empty. In old times it was quite a large village. In Abukhalo are preserved rock-cut dwellings, where the locals refugeed during enemy incursions.

XIII century, it already represented a large monastery complex. Particularly noteworthy is the Church of the Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary, which still has traces of painting. The monastery complex was described in the 19th and 20th centuries by Iason Tsitsishvili and Sergi Makalatia, according to whom the church had a fence, and inside there were rooms for monks. Monastic life interrupted in the XVII century was resurrected on June 17, 1997. In addition to the Kozipha Fathers' Monastery, the Ortubani, Kintsvisi, Samtsevisi, and Dzovreti complexes also represent important monastic ensembles.

As we have mentioned, the Dzama gorge was the nobility of Panaskerteli-Tsitsishvili. The feudal ancestral home of the Panaskertelis is connected with the historic Tao. They were the owners of the Tao in the IX-X centuries. The family name "Panaskerteli" was given because of the ownership of the Panaskert fortress. Panaskerteli moved from Tao to Shida Kartli in the XV century. Although we will not focus on the reasons for moving, there are several reasons (N. Berdzenishvili, From the history of the feudal family of Panaskerteli, Historical-Geographical Collection of Georgia, I, Tb. 1960 pp. 99-102) It should be noted that the newly established temples in the Dzama Gorge are a synthesis of historical and cultural memory. The new monastic complexes are analogous to the names of the temples in Tao-Klarjeti and therefore they have a special significance: Shatberdi, Bermukha, Bana, Opiza, Tskarostavi, Tbeti, Khandzta. The newly established temples repeat the Georgian architectural style of different eras: cross-domed, basilica, and wooden buildings. Noteworthy is the rock-cut temple in Sarkineti, named after Shio Mghvimeli, which was consecrated by Reverend Iob in 2011. The tradition of carving rock temples in Georgia has not existed since the XIV century. Sarkineti Monastery is distinguished by its wall painting.

One of the most important monastic complexes in the Gorge is the Shuano Monastery (located at an altitude of 1800 m), the construction of which began after the ruins of the basilica of the V-VI centuries was found. Of the newly established sanctuaries, the Mothers Monastery of Getsamania is important, which was built on the site of the ruins, which during the ancient times was the Ascension Temple. Ukrainian pilgrims made a great contribution to the construction.

The cross-domed church of Vakhtang Gorgasali is one of the most important of the new settlements of Dzama gorge. It is worth mentioning that there are not many temples in Georgia named after the great Georgian king: in the village of Sno in Kazbegi district (2006), in Tbilisi, Varketili

(the temple was built to immortalize the heroes killed in the 2008 war), in Rustavi (2010), in Munich (2001), in Batumi (2018). The name of Vakhtang Gorgasali is connected with the return of the lost territories, and the heroic struggle of the Georgian people against the Iranian invaders. During his reign (second half of the 5th century) the Georgian Church gained autocephaly, Tbilisi was declared the capital of Kartli, and the foreign orientation of Georgia was defined as the road to Byzantium, the road to Europe. Holy King Vakhtang Gorgasali could see and feel the great importance of the church. The establishment of the Church of the Holy King in the Dzama Gorge is of symbolic importance. The process of rebuilding the temple was accompanied by controversy and a miracle sent by the Lord. Construction began in 2013 and the first baptism took place here in 2018. The Vakhtang Gorgasali Temple repeats the medieval architectural style, the temple is finished and frescoes are being painted.

The monastic life opened in the Dzama Gorge, and the monks and nuns living in the old and new churches and monasteries are the creators of the spirit of the revival of the emptied gorge and are already the settling population (there are about 260 clergies in the 58 ecclesiastical-monasteries) guarding the gorge. All this causes dissatisfaction among the part of the society that is hostile to the church and tries to insult them with slander against the monks with thousands of ordered articles. During the investigation, it was revealed that the information spread on social networks and televisions, according to which the local residents are being harassed in the gorge and eco-migrants and the Ossetian population is leaving the area, is not true. If we observe the construction of monasteries in the Gorge, it started mainly from the beginning of the XXI century, when the area was completely emptied of locals. Georgian-Ossetian ethnic conflict (Russia-inspired) led to the fleeing of Ossetians. Timely action was needed to prevent the emptied gorge from being alienated (as many Georgian lands were alienated for 50 and 100 years). The Georgian Apostolic Church, which has always been the guardian of the nation and the state, the protection of Georgian lands, laid the foundation for the work of state importance and began to revive the monastic life in the gorge. Historically, the process of transferring lands to the church in Georgia was constantly carried out by kings and princes, and we can cite numerous examples and historical documents. Georgia, which is on the path of Europeanization and we try to reflect the values and mentality of a country of European values, it would be good to consider the forms of relations between church and state that are established in Europe, for example, churches separated from the state

usually take the form of voluntary associations, and their property is managed by guardians (who may be registered companies) under ordinary secular law. Such associations have no special status (State and Church in the Member States of the European Union, Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, Tbilisi, 2011, pp. 4-5). In important states of European countries, the state pays the salaries of church ministers, their property is tax-free. In France, for example, the church has to decide for itself how to raise funds and how to use them. The actual methods are different. Several examples: Funds are raised by the believers. Each local church manages its own resources, but the principle of solidarity operates to reduce the gap between rich and poor regions (State and Church in the Member States of the European Union, Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, Tbilisi, 2011, pp. 13-14). I think based on this small example we could point out that the monk-nuns of the valley are doing nothing illegal and against the country. The discretion of significant national work taking place in the Dzama Gorge reflects the lack of knowledge about the relationship between the Church and the state of different anti-Georgian organizations and individuals, and their actions are an attempt to mislead the public and discredit the Church. For example, the information is completely untrue regarding the seizure of agricultural lands by priests. In the published information astronomical figures of plots of land are specially presented in square meters to provoke public outrage. If we turn these numbers into hectares, we get a completely different picture. These farms are cultivated by local nuns and priests so that they can earn a living and endure from year to year. It should also be noted that the revival of monastic life, the improvement of infrastructure, and the growth of tourist flow, on the contrary, led to the activation of new hotels and agricultural activities by local residents. The youth who left the valley slowly returned to their paternal residence.

The revival of the monastic life in Georgia serves the idea of the spiritual development of the nation and the preservation of the territories of the country. The Georgian Church has always been the unifier of the country, the hope-giver to the nation. Churches and monasteries spread on the mountain slopes add a special touch to the beautiful nature of the Dzama.

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